

HYBRID WAR ON QATAR (2017-2020)

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DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.16358790>**Keywords**

Hybrid War, Blockade, GCC, FIFA 2022, Sun Tzu, Qatar

Article History

Received: 22 April, 2025

Accepted: 27 June, 2025

Published: 23 July, 2025

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Abstract

The ongoing debate on the concept and execution of hybrid war proves its efficacy if executed with meticulous planning. In contemporary times, the virtual blockade of Qatar on June 5, 2017, as decided by the governments of three neighbouring countries – Saudi Arabia, the United Arab Emirates, and Bahrain, alongside Egypt –was unprecedented in the region's history. The hybrid war imposed on Qatar was only meant to choke the country and impose a will on its leadership to accept specific demands without any question. This paper aims to investigate the causes and motives behind the imposition of a hybrid war on Qatar. To maintain originality and draw pertinent lessons through the lens of hybrid warfare, an appraisal tool, DIMPLE² (Diplomacy, Information, Moral, People, Leadership, Economy), has been deployed for a comprehensive and all-encompassing analysis of the blockade period.

INTRODUCTION

Qatar is a small peninsular state in the Persian (Arabian) Gulf. It gained independence from the fading British Empire in 1971. Soon after its independence, Qatar's leadership declined an offer to join the United Arab Emirates (UAE) and decided to maintain its political and territorial identity. Despite its small size and population, Qatar has emerged as a symbol of modernity amongst the Gulf countries. Qatar has demonstrated an enormous capacity to absorb the influx of multicultural and multi-ethnic workers into its ninety-one per cent expat population. Qatar, despite being a small nation in terms of geographical size and indigenous population, has consistently demonstrated its commitment to peace and stability. Qatar is always at the forefront of offering its services as a peacemaker. Whether it be the Doha Agreement between the US and the Afghan Taliban in February 2020, or the recent humanitarian truce between Hamas and Israel in November 2023, Qatar has consistently demonstrated its responsibility

as a nation.¹ Even if it was accused of supporting Hamas and Hezbollah at times.

Qatar, a relatively young Islamic state, is building itself from scratch because the colonial masters left it as a fishing village without any worthwhile development. Perhaps this is one reason that Qatar does not showcase any monuments of the colonial past, except in its national museums. Qatar proudly presents its values and cultural heritage in its architecture, the number of museums that it has developed, and at different international events that it regularly organises, particularly the mega sporting events like FIFA-2020, the World Handball Tournament (2014), Qatar Open Tennis Championship, and International Athletic Championship (2019).

Qatar is seen as a symbol of progress, development, tolerance, and resistance, following the basic principles of identity and independence laid down by the Emir for its people, in line with core Islamic values. Qatar launched an ambitious plan of

¹ Kobi Michael and Yoel Guzansky, Qatar under Siege: Regional Implications and Ramifications for the Palestinian arena, *The Institute of National Security Studies*, (June 12, 2017).

development as part of its Qatar Nation Vision (QNV-2030), which was aimed at, “modernizing the state while preserving its values and heritage, fulfilling the aspirations of the people now and in the future, maintaining the quality of foreign workers, grow the economy with investments in social sector to directly benefit the people, and ensure mitigation of climate change.”² Since its launch in July 2008, Qatar has religiously followed and is striving to achieve its stated objectives in all five domains.

Qatar is a significant player in the Gulf region due to its substantial oil and gas reserves. However, the major regional players, the Kingdom of Saudi Arabia (KSA) and the UAE, view Qatar’s independent foreign policy and its efforts to project itself as a modern and progressive state as being against their interests.³ Therefore, the two leading nations of the GCC, in concert with Bahrain and Egypt, decided to impose a physical blockade of their relatively minor neighbour, Qatar. The blockade was not only imposed on its sole land border with KSA, but also on its air routes, sea routes, trade relations, bilateral relations, and all multilateral relations. The blockade had a significant impact on regional stability and security, particularly at a time when Qatar was preparing for the 2022 FIFA World Cup.

Interestingly, the blockading countries deployed nearly all elements of hybrid warfare against Qatar, except for kinetic application, which had been planned but held back due to Qatar’s exceptional display of statesmanship and resilience among its populace. However, the Qataris may never forget June 5, 2017, a date that will go down in their history as a mark of betrayal by the brotherly nations. It is a stark reminder to the students of political science that “we have no eternal allies, and we have no perpetual enemies. Our interests are eternal and perpetual, and those interests we must follow.”⁴ However, Qatar’s leadership displayed sober and responsible behaviour, and therefore, does not celebrate or observe an

anniversary on the day, particularly since the lifting of the blockade in December 2021.

To draw pertinent lessons from the recently resolved conflict of the blockade of Qatar, it is necessary to view the entire episode through the lens of hybrid warfare and all its tenets that the initiators deployed. Perhaps Qatar’s strategic defiance of the KSA and UAE-led quartet’s strategic dominance of the GCC will go a long way in strengthening the small nation’s resolve to preserve its sovereignty through resolute leadership, astute diplomacy, and the unwavering support of its people.

Narrative of Events: The Blockade of Qatar

While the Western world with a non-Muslim majority was stocking up foodstuffs at a subsidised rate for their Muslim population during their Holy month of Ramadan in June 2017, the state of Qatar, a Muslim majority state, was put under socio-political and economic blockade by a group of other Muslim countries, denying it accesses to essential food items, instantly. The initiators deployed nearly all the elements of hybrid warfare to choke Qatar and fuel an insurgency-like situation in the country, which over ninety per cent of expats inhabit.

The practical blockade of Qatar by three neighbouring nations –KSA, UAE, and Bahrain, alongside Egypt – at the dawn of June 5, 2017, was unprecedented in the region's history. The regional environment suddenly became tense and uncertain, and shocked the world. This extreme action against a geographically small peninsular nation was seen in utter disbelief, particularly during the Holy month of Ramadan. Such an action was only meant to choke Qatar and impose its will on its leadership to accept its demand without any question.

According to most analysts, Qatar's role in supporting various political movements and its relations with countries like Iran were significant factors in the dispute. The blockade aimed to pressure Qatar into changing its policies and aligning more closely with

² Qatar National Vision 2030, <https://www.gco.gov.qa/en/about-qatar/national-vision2030/> (accessed November 30, 2023).

³ Alex MacDonald, “Qatar blockade: What caused it and why is it coming to an end?” (Middle East Eye, January 5, 2021).

⁴ Lord Palmerston, British Prime Minister (1855–8, 1859–65), speaking to House of Commons, March 1, 1848, (accessed November 21, 2023).

the positions of the other Gulf Cooperation Council (GCC) members.⁵ Moreover, Qatar's close ties with Iran and Turkey were not seen as aligning with the GCC's vision in the domains of military, political, social, and economic spheres. Also, Qatar's prime media network, Al Jazeera, was blamed for supporting extremist and terrorist organisations in the region.⁶ Qatar outrightly rejected these allegations; however, one must appreciate the Qatari leadership for its handling of the situation, despite the country facing an existential threat.

The leadership of Qatar remained calm, composed, and responsive to the evolving situation. It did not create panic among its residents, nor did it require any emergency assistance from another country. Qatar launched an exhaustive diplomatic manoeuvre and rightly insisted that the matter could be resolved through dialogue. Concurrently, Qatar has made it clear that it intends to pursue its independent foreign policy and is not willing to compromise on its principles. Additionally, Qatar did not announce any reciprocal measures in response to the unjust sanctions imposed on it by any of the blockading countries. The initiators of the hybrid war deployed nearly all the non-military elements of warfare against a geographically small brotherly nation. Even during the global COVID-19 crisis, when medical supplies were being shipped into Western Europe and the US from China and Russia, the state of Qatar remained cut off from at least three sides: land, air, and sea, since June 5, 2017, due to the blockade by the blockading nations.

Kuwait took the lead in launching a diplomatic mission, and its efforts were applauded mainly by all the neutral nations. Turkey responded in kind, and its Parliament authorised the deployment of additional troops to defend Qatar, should the situation reach that level. Iran also offered its ports to maintain the supply of essential food imports. However, Qatar's Chambers of Commerce and Industries maintained

that there is no shortage of food items and building materials, and there is no cause for concern of any sort.⁷

Defining Hybrid Warfare

To define the concept of hybrid warfare, various terms are employed, including hybrid conflict, hybrid threat, hybrid approaches, hybrid efforts, grey zone techniques, and even 4th and 5th Generation warfare.⁸ It encompasses all other terms to explain the nature and evolving character of war in the contemporary age. It is now universally accepted that the terminology of hybrid warfare represents the application of a variety of means deployed against the target state to achieve the politico-military objectives of the initiators. This hybridity in the elements of war has now made it a favourite option for strategists and practitioners in contemporary wars.

The strategies adopted as part of hybrid warfare aim to weaken the target state without using kinetic means, especially in the case of rich but smaller states, such as Qatar, which remain vulnerable to regional developments. Likewise, a hybrid threat poses a serious challenge to a stable international system because the adversary may employ Non-State Actors (NSAs) to achieve its objectives against relatively smaller and weaker states.

The initiators of the synergistic application of hybrid warfare aim to inflict effects in multiple domains on target states by utilising a range of tangible and intangible avenues. While tangible elements of warfare include visible military hardware, the intangible elements, which an enemy operates from within and is invisible to, are often more damaging and effective. These elements comprise the hybrid warfare domain, which has a vast canvas. According to Hoffman, "analyses of the international security environment have increasingly drawn attention to what is often referred to as the grey zone."⁹ Moreover, the term hybridity refers not only to combat situations

⁵ Alex MacDonald, "Qatar blockade: What caused it and why is it coming to an end?" (Middle East Eye, January 5, 2021).

⁶ Jared Malsin, "In the Eyes of the Storm: Can Al Jazeera Survive the Gulf Crisis?" Time, August 21, 2017.

⁷ Arwa Ibrahim, "Qatar Beating the blockade: How it prevailed over a siege" (Aljazeera, June 5, 2020).

⁸ Explainer: What is 'hybrid warfare' and what is meant by 'grey zone'? (The conversation, June 17, 2019).

⁹ Frank G. Hoffman, "Examining Complex Forms of Conflict: Gray Zone and Hybrid Challenges," (PRISM 7, no. 4 (November 2018): 31-47).

and the strategies and tactics of rival states but also to the responses that nations and their allies employ to counter these approaches. Another concept related to this type of threat is irregular military action, which describes several phenomena, including unconventional and asymmetric military approaches, airborne sabotage, guerrilla warfare tactics during counterinsurgencies, uprisings, civil wars and revolutionary actions.

The concept of hybridity in warfare dates back to the Chinese sage Sun Tzu, who emphasised the importance of achieving victory over the enemy without resorting to direct combat. Sun Tzu considered war a sombre affair for the state and a last resort for subduing one's enemies. He was of the view that if war becomes necessary, then it must be short and swift because prolonged wars do not serve the purpose, particularly for the initiators. Moreover, the canvas of hybrid war encompasses all domains, including administrative, legal, financial, cyber, informational, and societal aspects.

The term "hybrid warfare" has been in use by U.S. military experts for over two decades. It was first used in 2002 by Major William J. Nemeth during his examination of the Chechen Insurgency. It employs a combination of political warfare, alongside conventional warfare, irregular warfare, and cyber warfare. It also uses a range of methods to influence the people of the target state, including media campaigns that disseminate misinformation, diplomatic manoeuvres, manipulation of international institutions, and even interference with its electoral system. However, like any other strategic terminology, an ambiguity existed over the concept, context, and meaning. The recent conflicts in the Middle East and the ongoing Russia-Ukraine war have led experts to conclude that hybrid warfare is a conflict where stakeholders synergise their hard and soft power capabilities and resources to achieve their political objectives.

The employment of hybrid warfare is gaining ground among the global strategic and security community due to its diverse applications, even if the concept

dates to ancient times. It offers numerous avenues for initiators to achieve their objectives within a short timeframe by deploying a combination of kinetic and non-kinetic elements of warfare.

One of the primary politico-military objectives of any hybrid warfare campaign remains to persuade the target state to accept the demands of the initiators, either during negotiations or following potential execution. Perhaps the central idea of hybrid warfare originated from Sun Tzu's dictum that efforts must be made to win the war without fighting.¹⁰ However, for most of the 21st Century, wars have seen more violence right from the beginning of the conflict rather than being used as a last resort. Unfortunately, there has not been much effort to avoid physical violence, particularly by the relatively stronger nations against the weaker and smaller states.

The concept of hybrid warfare gained prominence soon after the conflictual events between Russia and Ukraine in 2014.¹¹ Since it employs a range of methods and strategies, it has immediately become a favourite tool among strategists, practitioners, and academics. Like any other strategic term, hybrid warfare also lacks a universal definition; however, many scholars and practitioners have defined it as the combination of conventional and unconventional military tools.¹² In the same context, various terminologies are used to describe the concept of hybrid warfare, a phenomenon that has attracted both planners and executioners. However, its definitions and applications have been shaped by the nature of conflicts in different regions. The expanded canvas of hybrid warfare offers a range of avenues where initiators can deploy their elements, including regime change operations, coercive diplomacy, economic sanctions, cyber-attacks, irregular military operations, and international pressure tactics, as well as the deployment of NSAs as proxies.

The applications of hybrid warfare have been debated in the region for the last few years, perhaps because a relatively minor state, Qatar, was under the cloud of some of the region's major powers, supported by a few extra-regional states. This author opines that the

¹⁰ Sun Tzu, "The Art of War", ed. James Clavell (Lahore: Combine Printers Ltd., 1983, 45).

¹¹ James K. Whiter, Making Sense of Hybrid Warfare, 2016, (Connections, Vol. 15, no. 2, Spring 2016, 73-87).

¹² Erik Reichborn-Kjennerud & Patrick Cullen, What is Hybrid Warfare? (Policy Brief, 1/2016).

deployment of hybrid warfare elements against a brotherly Islamic state was primarily aimed at the change of regime by alienating the people of Qatar and having a government of its own choice that would follow the line of regional powers in its foreign relations. Hence, the centre of gravity (CG) was identified as the leadership of Qatar, as it enjoyed unwavering support from the people. Diplomacy was the core of the country's deterrent value as a peacemaker in the region and beyond.

Hybrid Mannerism of the Blockade of Qatar

The KSA-led quartet deployed nearly all the tenets of hybrid warfare against Qatar, except the kinetic application, which may have been a part of the plan but was not executed. This part of the paper examines the tenets of hybrid warfare deployed against Qatar during the blockade, which lasted over three years. For originality and objectivity in the process, this author has developed an expanded strategic appraisal tool: DIMPLE² (Diplomacy and Deterrence, Information and Intelligence, Moral and Military, People and Politics, Leadership and Legal, and Economy and Energy), which greatly helped in looking at the development of the events through the lens of hybrid warfare, and Qatar's measured response during the entire period of the blockade. It may be necessary to mention that certain quarters refer to the whole episode of strained relations between the blockading countries and Qatar as a 'siege'. However, for this research, the term 'blockade' will be used.

Analyses on DIMPLE²

Diplomacy and Deterrence. This author opines that diplomacy and deterrence are the primary and essential tools of any state, which can ensure the territorial integrity and sovereignty of the state. Suppose diplomacy and deterrence are effectively playing their role. In that case, there is a high probability that the state will achieve strategic stability at the regional level and avoid wars and conflicts with disputed nations. However, the conflict can still be managed in the event of deterrence failure, because positive diplomacy with alliances and strategic partners can play a decisive role in averting the conflict from escalating into violence. Whereas, if both diplomacy and deterrence fail, then there is a very high probability of a violent confrontation,

particularly in the presence of an unresolved dispute. This proved efficacious in the case of Qatar's blockade by the neighbouring nations. Diplomacy played a proper role in being the frontline defence of Qatar. The diplomatic corps of Qatar provided the necessary support around the clock, from the onset of the crisis until it ultimately subsided. Qatar's diplomatic efforts included bilateral and multilateral contacts and agreements with diverse stakeholders across multiple domains, including foreign policy, economy, military, and even sports, primarily to ensure an unhindered preparation for FIFA 2020. Interestingly, Qatar's diplomatic overtures bore fruit in each of the domains above, and hence Qatar emerged from the crisis without firing a single bullet. The same will be discussed in detail in the following paragraphs.

No sooner was the blockade announced in the early hours of June 5, 2017, than Qatar immediately requested that Turkey activate its strategic partnership accords. The age-old friendly ties with Turkey proved beneficial in averting what appeared to be an impending violent conflict. Concurrently, a peace initiative was launched by Kuwait, and Iran provided equally strong support, which strengthened Qatar's ability to withstand the pressure in an unprecedented situation.

Qatar's military diplomacy has been a crucial element in maintaining its deterrent capability and ensuring its readiness to respond to potential threats. Despite the limitations that come with its relatively small size and strength, Qatar has effectively leveraged its military diplomacy to bolster its defence posture and regional influence. Qatar's deterrent capacity rests not only on its military capability but also on the support from its alliance partners, its immense soft power based on its robust economy, and its efforts for peace in the region. Qatar is always seen at the forefront for providing its services for peace efforts during wars and conflicts of other countries, like talks between the US and Taliban, Hamas and Israel, etc.

On the other hand, despite extreme enmity during the period of crisis, the Emir did not forget to send a message of condolences to the UAE Leader on the sad

demise of his mother.¹³ The Emir of Qatar ensured that religious values were maintained even if the political environment was strained due to an unjust blockade, of which the UAE was a leading accomplice. In fact, in Arab culture, these gestures hold significant importance.

On the other hand, as a peaceful country, Qatar has developed a deep understanding and cooperation with the US on counterterrorism. There were dedicated teams from both sides, which were working together. Moreover, Qatar is home to one of the largest United States Air Force (USAF) bases in the region, and the military relations between the two are deep and of a strategic nature. This relationship was further strengthened during the period of blockade and may have contributed to averting a war-like situation, along with other factors. Moreover, it was reiterated that the US-Qatar strategic dialogue initiative reflects the deepening relationship between the two countries across multiple domains. By focusing on political, economic, security, educational, and cultural cooperation, the dialogue seeks to enhance collaboration and address shared interests and challenges.

Qatar's multipronged diplomacy also included contacts with Russia. In February 2018, the Emir of Qatar held a productive meeting with Yunus-bek Yevkurov, the President of the Russian Republic of Ingushetia, to review cooperation in the economic, trade, and investment domains. President Yevkurov also presented a personal letter of invitation from President Putin to the Emir, extending an official invitation for a visit to Russia.

Intelligence and Information

The blockading countries executed their plans with extreme secrecy, surprising not only Qatar but also the rest of the world. The primary targets were the leadership and the people, as dictated by the principles of hybrid warfare. Therefore, the time

chosen was the Holy Month of Ramadan, so that the people could be swayed against the leadership if it failed to ensure the provision of critical supplies of essential food items. However, the plan was unable to impress the people of Qatar, primarily because the government struggled with the supply chain management of critical food items.

In the information domain of hybrid warfare, Qatar managed to convince the people at home and abroad that the demands of the blockading nations are unjust, and that the blockade is illegal and uncalled for. Whereas the blockading nations, despite spending millions on a propaganda campaign, could not persuade many of the regional countries, in general, and the major powers, in particular, to abandon Qatar. For the same purpose, much before the Qatar blockade became effective, it was revealed that on February 5, 2017, "Daniel Kawczynski, a British parliamentarian, was paid 15,000 British pounds (\$20,700) to help organize an anti-Qatar conference in London..... an attempt to gather support for a coup in Qatar and accused Saudi Arabia and the UAE of funding it."¹⁴ Finally, the initiators decided, as the Minister said, "the beginning was an ambush. The only thing is, I don't think they calculated correctly. We have enhanced our bilateral relations worldwide. So, you may say that the plan failed. All their 13 demands."¹⁵

Moral and Military

Qatar, a small Peninsula state, does not have large armed forces to defend its small territory, which lacks strategic depth, and has no land borders with any of its allies. And, when "the four countries imposed wide-ranging sanctions on Qatar in June 2017, accusing it of supporting terrorism and of being too close to Iran. They closed their land borders, air and seaports, and airspace to Qataris."¹⁶ Perhaps Qatar was in a similar situation to that faced by Kuwait at the hands of Iraq in August 1990. Therefore, the

¹³ Qatar emir sends condolences to UAE leader, (AFP, January 29, 2018).

¹⁴ Anti-Qatar Conference, (Aljazeera, 2017).
<https://www.aljazeera.com/news/2018/2/18/qatars-blockade-in-2017-day-by-day-developments> (accessed November 20, 2023).

¹⁵ Lally Weymouth, "Qatar to Saudi Arabia: Quit Trying to Overthrow our government," (The Washington Post, February 2, 2018).

¹⁶ UN human rights expert urges four Gulf states to lift unilateral sanctions against Qatar, (November 12, 2020).

Emir of Kuwait made valiant efforts to defuse the tension between Gulf neighbours and bring normalcy to the region.

Qatar was indeed faced with an existential threat and lacked a deterrent effect due to its limited military strength. However, Qatar's real deterrent value was based on its high moral ground, unflinching support from its allies, and the resolute backing of its people for its leadership. Qatar wasted no time in implementing the 2014 military cooperation accord with another brotherly nation, Turkey, which allowed for a greater presence of the Turkish military in Qatar.

Qatar's al-Attiyah put the entire episode in perspective and categorically stated that "Saudi Arabia and the United Arab Emirates had intentions to invade Qatar at the beginning of a diplomatic crisis that erupted in June.... Gulf neighbours have 'tried everything' to destabilise the country, but their intentions to invade were 'defused' by Qatar.¹⁷ Qatar's military diplomacy proved efficacious in a highly precarious situation, as reflected in the Minister of Defense's assertions.

People and Politics

Qatar's population at the time of the blockade on June 5, 2017, was approximately 2.7 million, of which nearly ninety per cent were expatriate workers, both skilled and unskilled. However, the entire population, citizens and residents, stood firmly behind the leadership of Qatar's Ruler, Shaikh Tamim, throughout the crisis. Unlike Kuwait's crisis during Iraq's invasion in 1991, where the people fled the country without money and materials, the people of Qatar not only remained in the country but also continued to perform their daily duties and businesses as usual to keep the FIFA 2022 on track.

Despite propaganda campaigns against Qatar's ability to cope with the crisis, there was no panic on the streets of any city, and no long queues were observed at the airport or the shopping centres. Except for some dairy and poultry products of Almarai, which were imported through the land borders from Saudi

Arabia, there were no issues with supply chain management. One could see a beeline of logistics vehicles from all the neighbouring states, both at sea and from the air. This ensured that there was no dearth of food items in the besieged state.¹⁸

The people's response to the Emir's call to maintain calm and continue their everyday lives was positive and exemplary for any other nation currently facing or likely to face such a crisis in the future. The Emir's famous dictum, 'Everything is going to be all right,' appeared in the parks and even on the Sheraton's pyramid and proved incredibly motivating and self-assuring.

The KSA-led quartet targeted the people of Qatar, knowing fully well that little over ninety per cent of the population comprises temporary residents, mostly foreigners from developing countries: skilled and unskilled workers, and may be deterred easily from leaving the country once the crisis begins. Moreover, the perception was created through the narrative building that the state of Qatar would soon be turned into Kuwait in the 1990s. However, the initiators failed to impress the people of Qatar, who adored the Emir for his endless love and care for the residents and citizens alike.

The people of Qatar remained firmly behind their leadership and did not leave the country, either at the beginning or during the crisis, until it was finally resolved in December 2020. Al-Attiyah acknowledged the same. "They thought they could strike hard and bend the Qatari people. But the people showed solidarity and became more resilient.... They tried to provoke the tribes. They used mosques against us. Then they tried to get some puppets to bring in and replace our leaders."¹⁹

The human sufferings during the period of the blockade were different, from psycho-social to emotional bearings, and the UN Special Rapporteur amply highlighted economic challenges to financial harassment.

"The sanctions had harmed the ability of Qataris to enjoy several fundamental rights and freedoms

¹⁷ Lally Weymouth, "Qatar to Saudi Arabia: Quit Trying to Overthrow our government," (The Washington Post, February 2, 2018).

¹⁸ Arwa Ibrahim, "Beating the blockade: How Qatar prevailed over a siege." (Aljazeera June 5, 2020).

¹⁹ Lally Weymouth, "Qatar to Saudi Arabia: Quit Trying to Overthrow our government," (The Washington Post, February 2, 2018).

connected to family life, education, work, health, private property, religion, expression and access to justice... including couples in mixed marriages and their children, migrant workers who lost their jobs and benefits..."²⁰

Since the initiators had identified the intimate relationship between the leadership and the people, the attack was directed against these two essential components of the state. However, the KSA-led quartet gained nothing despite having rightly identified the CG of the state of Qatar. The initiators were willing to put regional stability and security at risk for the sake of their political gains against a relatively small neighbouring state, which had powerful credentials on the peace-making canvas of the region and beyond.

Leadership and Legal

The leadership of Qatar's Emir played a pivotal role in leading the resistance to the initiators' plot to overthrow his government and avoid a full-fledged invasion of the small Peninsular state. This author considers leadership to be the most crucial element in a successful resistance to the unjust demands of the blockading nations. Qatar's Emir maintained calm throughout the entire blockade period and remained committed to sustaining pressure and overcoming the crisis from start to finish. Contrary to the assumptions of the aggressors, the Emir of Qatar is still too young to face a crisis of such magnitude and will eventually succumb to the demands of the blockading countries. Perhaps an analogy can be drawn to Soviet leader Nikita Khrushchev's assessment of President John F. Kennedy during the Cuban Missile Crisis of 1962. However, the initiators were amazed to see the behaviour of the Qatari leadership, which remained cool, calm, and composed (C3), in sending a positive message to the populace. The Emir took the lead and decided to speak to the people directly through a rare media appearance. The Qatari leader sounded very confident, delivering a message of peace and insisting on a peaceful resolution to the ongoing dispute. Expectedly, people came forward to support their

leadership and hence thwarted any attempt to create political instability in the country.

On legal grounds, Qatar's case was extreme. Despite deliberate efforts to malign the country in support of terror activities of certain Non-State Actors, and the state of Iran, the KSA-led quartet failed to impress upon any international organisation to sanction the already-blocked country.

Qatar blamed the UAE for undermining its currency, and "Banque Havilland tried to weaken its currency, the riyal, by submitting what the statement called fraudulent quotes to foreign-exchange platforms in New York, allegedly intended to disrupt indices and markets where significant Qatari assets and investors are located."²¹ Qatar has also initiated "legal action against the four blockading countries before the International Court of Justice (ICJ), International Civil Aviation Organisation (ICAO) and the World Trade Organisation (WTO)."²²

Economy and Energy

The robust economy of Qatar demonstrated remarkable resilience in the face of the extreme hostility from the blockading countries. The blockade of Qatar by the neighbouring countries was aimed at choking the small peninsular state and installing a puppet government to make it a pliant state. However, Qatar stood the test of time. There is no denying that the blockade had a profoundly negative impact on the economy and Qatar's preparations for FIFA 2022. However, Qatar faced the situation with courage and bold decisions. During the three years of the blockade, Qatar is estimated to have suffered a loss of at least USD 43 billion. However, despite enormous suffering, Qatar's government did not slow down the development works; instead, it made good use of the opportunity to improve its food security and industrial production. "Qatar's achievement of the top spot for food security in the Middle East and its 13th place globally, according to the latest Global Food Security Index by the Economist Intelligence Unit, underscores its significant progress in ensuring food security."²³ Qatar's successful efforts in achieving

²⁰ UN human rights expert urges four Gulf states to lift unilateral sanctions against Qatar, (November 12, 2020).

²¹ Qatar sues UAE, Saudi, Luxembourg banks over riyal 'manipulation' (Aljazeera, April 8, 2019).

²² Qatar sues UAE, Saudi, Luxembourg banks over riyal 'manipulation' (Aljazeera, April 8, 2019).

²³ Arwa Ibrahim, "Beating the blockade: How Qatar prevailed over a siege." (Aljazeera, June 5, 2020).

such a high-ranking note in food security reflected its resolve to address challenges and its commitment to maintaining stability and resilience in its food supply system.

In other sectors of the economy, too, Qatar moved swiftly and, within months, made its newly built Hamad Port operational. Since Qatar was heavily dependent on imports of food and other essential items, the port played a crucial role in ensuring the availability of basic supplies and commodities through maritime routes. Likewise, Qatar Airways also played a significant role, despite losing air routes and air passages, in meeting the essential requirements of perishable items. Interestingly, Qatar relieved itself of an over-dependence on regional actors for critical food supplies and hence developed stronger ties with friendly countries like Turkey and Iran, which stood by Qatar in testing times.²⁴

In the energy sector, Qatar's critical infrastructure, including its leading LNG company, RasGas, was targeted by cyberattacks as part of a hybrid campaign. However, Qatar was able to develop resilient countermeasures to safeguard its energy sector.

Conclusion

The Blockade of Qatar lasted for over three years, unfortunately, and even during the COVID-19 pandemic. However, Qatar put up a brave face in testing times and remained committed to preparing itself for FIFA 2022, without showing any signs of stress under pressure, coercion, or compulsion. Qatar stood its ground and, with the support of its people and its regional partners, maintained its stance that it does not support extremism and terrorism in any form, and only supports the just struggles of the oppressed people in the conflict zones.

The hybrid war imposed on Qatar in the form of a blockade was aimed at economic and political isolation by the brotherly GCC nations. However, the illegal blockade had to be lifted under international pressure led by the US, because Qatar did not budge from its principled stand. The initiators of the hybrid war could not substantiate the allegations about Qatar supporting terror outfits in the region. Moreover,

Qatar's allies, Turkey and Iran, provided the much-needed support to overcome the disrupted food supplies.

The hybrid war imposed on Qatar was only meant to choke the country and impose its will on its leadership to accept its demand without any question. However, the inseparable linkage between the leadership and the people, executed through bold diplomacy in testing times, thwarted any attempt to destabilise the region. This author opines that Qatar won the first round without a single shot fired, denying its much larger adversaries the accomplishment of their political objectives through a resolute response by the leadership, people, and proactive diplomacy.

KSA-led quartet unsuccessfully employed all available non-kinetic means to hurt Qatar so that it abandons its independent foreign policy and its pursuit to organize mega events such as FIFA 2022. However, what the initiators of the hybrid war on Qatar could not achieve in over three years of blockade was to shake the people of Qatar or make them even think against their beloved Emir. Therefore, after three and a half years of campaigning, the initiators ended the campaign once none of the stated objectives had been achieved. Instead, Qatar emerged from the blockade as much stronger and more independent than ever before. Perhaps, the blockade of Qatar helped the peninsular nation to invest heavily in food security and industrial development. Now that the embargo has been lifted and the political situation in the GCC is near normalisation, Qatar is far more confident, resilient, and self-sustaining.

The other smaller nations of the region and beyond can draw pertinent lessons from the blockade of Qatar by the neighbouring countries in multiple domains. For instance, Qatar's moral position was strong enough to convince the people at home and major stakeholders abroad that it is a peace-loving nation and does not support terrorism or extremism in any form. Qatar has proved this aspect on several occasions by voluntarily organising peace talks between warring nations. Moreover, the people's support for its leadership in times of crisis provides ample evidence of the Emir's efforts for the well-being

²⁴ Giorgio Cafiero, founder of Gulf State Analytics, [https://www.aljazeera.com/news/2020/6/5/](https://www.aljazeera.com/news/2020/6/5/beating-the-)

[blockade-how-qatar-prevailed-over-a-siege](https://www.aljazeera.com/news/2020/6/5/beat-the-blockade-how-qatar-prevailed-over-a-siege) (accessed November 24, 2023).

of its people. Lastly, the diplomatic approaches adopted by Qatar proved to be a game-changer during the entire period of the blockade.

Interestingly, the initiators of the hybrid warfare against a relatively minor and peace-loving neighbour achieved nothing but embarrassment and had to end the blockade after little over three years, resuming normal diplomatic relations at all forums.

The initiators rightly identified Qatar's centre of gravity (CG) in its leadership, due to its unwavering support of the people and diplomatic goodwill, stemming from the peacemaker role that the country has been playing in the region and beyond. Therefore, the initiators decided to launch multiple elements of hybrid warfare simultaneously to achieve their political objective within a short timeframe. While the non-kinetic aspects were put into action in a surprise move, the kinetic elements were placed in standby mode to exert maximum pressure on the relatively minor neighbouring nation.

Retrospectively, there is little doubt now that the initiators had rightly identified the CG, achieved a perfect surprise in their execution, and expected a quick result due to adequate regional support for their unjust and uncalled-for actions. However, they failed in their assessment of the Qatari leadership's capability and capacity to absorb and deliver.

Moreover, the initiator's evaluation of the resolve of the people of Qatar to deal with a crisis of such magnitude proved fatal for their acts. Hence, the initiators failed right at the beginning of the execution phase, primarily due to the unexpected and measured responses from both the leadership and the people. Yet they persisted, and the blockade continued for over three years without achieving a single objective from their list of thirteen demands. Perhaps, the initiators ignored the golden precepts of the Chinese sage Sun Tzu, who prophesied that knowing the enemy and knowing yourself is of utmost importance before executing a campaign.

Recommendation

Since it may not be the last time such a situation is created for political reasons by the relatively stronger regional powers, it is essential that the entire events that took place between June 2017 and December 2020 be thoroughly studied and relevant lessons drawn to meet such challenges in the future.

Moreover, Qatar's response to emerging challenges must also be analysed for the sake of enduring peace and the security of other regional countries, particularly the smaller states.

